

Terahertz substrate integrated waveguide wideband antenna for medical imaging and inter-satellite communications

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Abstract— In this paper, two different types of graphene based rectangular patch antennas are designed for broadband terahertz applications. First a patch antenna is modeled using copper metal for terahertz applications. The simulation results show a degraded reflection coefficient due to the use of copper. The patch antenna results are improved when graphene material is used, which has good conductivity as demonstrated through simulations. Time domain solver of CST MWS software is used to evaluate the performance of the SIW patch antennas. The results obtained with CST are compared with simulations using HFSS to further validate the design.

Keywords—Terahertz, SIW, graphene, broadband, antenna patch

I. INTRODUCTION

The substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) structure, has a good resolution and good performance for many applications. Compared with conventional planar technology, SIW structures exhibit low loss and high power handling [1-6]. Several SIW circuits have been designed and implemented for wireless communications, such as a SIW antenna for ISM band applications [7], this design was simulated and measured and has a good agreement between results. However, this antenna produces low gains for the two resonant frequencies, and uses two coaxial inputs, one per frequency band. Another broadband antenna with low gain is simulated and measured in [17]. Diverse SIW circuits can be found in the literature; like resonators, couplers, duplexers and power dividers, as in [8-9].

The terahertz application band corresponds to a portion of optoelectronic systems, including frequencies in the range from 1 THz to 16 THz [10]. Optical spectrum systems are in constant use by the scientific community for generation and imagery of terahertz (THz) radiation, with numerous applications in spectroscopy, imaging, sensing, astronomy and spectroscopy [11-13].

In order to obtain a high performance circuit, copper can be replaced for graphene, resulting in improved terahertz circuits. The discovery of graphene is a breakthrough in the development of THz devices and applications [14].

In this communication, an antenna design is proposed, shown in fig. 1 with its geometry according to table I. Section two contains graphene material properties and formulation. In section three, simulation results of the substrate integrated waveguide antenna are shown. Finally conclusions are provided in section four.

Fig. 1. (a) Top view Antenna1; (b) Bottom view of the two proposed antennas; (c) Top view Antenna 2

TABLE I. GEOMETRY PARAMETER

Parameter		a	b	R1	R2	L1	L2
Value[um]		21	33	12	16	32	5
W1	W2	W3	W4	d	p		
2	1.5	2	3	0.6	1.1		

II. FORMULATION AND RESULTS

A. Graphene material

A graphene sheet is a two-dimensional material composed of carbon atoms bonded in hexagonal structures. Its surface conductivity can be represented using the well-known Kubo formalism and it consists of two terms intra-band conductivity and inter-band conductivity [15]. The intra-band term can be calculated as

$$\sigma_{intra} = -j \frac{e^2 K_B T}{\pi h^2 (\omega - j2T)} \left[\frac{\mu_c}{K_B T} + 2 \text{Ln} \left(e^{\frac{\mu_c}{K_B T}} + 1 \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

and the inter-band conductivity is

$$\sigma_{inter} = -j \frac{e^2}{4\pi h} \ln \left[\frac{2|\mu_c| - (\omega - j2\Gamma)h}{2|\mu_c| + (\omega - j2\Gamma)h} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where K_B is the Boltzmann constant, this is the reduced Planck's constant, e is the electron charge, ω is the angular frequency, Γ is the scattering rate, T is the temperature and μ_c is the chemical potential. The intra-band conductivity dominates the value of total conductivity in the THz band, whereas the inter-band term has no significant effect on the total surface conductivity within this band. Hence, the conductivity of graphene can be expressed by using the only intraband term.[16]

Fig. 2. Real part of graphene's conductivity.

Fig. 3. Imaginary part of graphene's conductivity.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the effect of changing graphene chemical potential on the real and imaginary part of the surface conductivity. It depends on the carrier density, which can be controlled by an electric bias field. Increasing chemical potential leads to the increase in surface conductivity of graphene, which shifts device resonances to higher

frequencies. Fig. 4 shows the relationship between chemical potential and bias voltage.

Fig. 4 Relationship between bias voltage and chemical potential.

Fig. 5. Reflections coefficients of the two types materials of antenna

According to Fig. 5, which shows the reflection coefficient of the patch antenna, and improvement in S11 level is obtained when using the graphene material instead of copper. From this result, S11 can be below a -10dB when using graphene. Graphene shows good conductivity at terahertz frequencies.

B. Antenna design and results

In this part we have modeled a two patches antennas, the first is a simple antenna without SIW, simulated using two software, HFSS and CST. The two methods used, namely finite element and integral method are in good agreement. The antenna design in Fig. 1(a) can be made to work at terahertz frequencies. Fig. 5 shows the reflection coefficient can be optimized to be at about -10db. To improve these results, a SIW cavity is added around the antenna as shown in Fig.1 (b). The simulation results show an improvement in impedance matching, with a return loss of about -10dB.

The proposed antenna is simulated using the finite element method and integral method. The electric field diagram of the proposed antenna at 4 THz is shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 7 shows the simulated radiation pattern for the antenna at 4 THz.

Fig. 6. E-field distribution of the proposed antennas (a) E-field without SIW cavity (b) E-field with SIW cavity

Fig. 7. 3-D radiation patterns ; (a) 3-D radiation pattern of a simple antenna patch without SIW cavity (b) 3-D radiation pattern of proposed antenna with SIW cavity

Fig. 8 shows the reflection coefficient obtained when varying w_1 and w_2 according to the substrate integrated waveguide cavity in Fig. 1(c). The SIW cavity increases antenna gain, from 3.12 dB at 4 THz without the SIW cavity to 5.34 dB at 4 THz with SIW cavity.

Fig. 8. Reflection coefficient according to the variation of w_1 and w_2

Fig. 9. Reflection coefficient of proposed antenna for varying chemical potential

To explore the usefulness of tunable surface conductivity of graphene in microwave antenna design, simulated reflection coefficients (S11) of the SIW proposed antenna with $W_1 = 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ and $w_2 = 1 \mu\text{m}$, is presented in Fig.9. An improvement in reflection coefficient is obtained when increasing the chemical potential.

III. VALIDATED RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this part, the validation of the designed SIW antenna is done by simulating the same antennas with the HFSS software and comparing the results with those obtained with CST. Figs. 10 and 11 provide the simulation results in terms of reflection coefficient and radiation pattern (E-plane and H-plane), respectively. According Fig. 10, a good agreement of S11 can be observed when comparing the CST and HFSS results. A slight deviation in side lobe level is found, as shown in fig. 11, a good agreement is observed for E-plane and H-plane radiation patterns gains from Fig. 11. The simulation of the proposed antennas have a maximum gain of 6 dB and can vary to 1.2 dB between the 2 and 20 THz frequency range.

Fig. 10. Reflection coefficient of the proposed antenna, simulated using CST and HFSS

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11. Radiation patterns (a) E-plane (b) H-plane at 4 THz obtained from CST and HFSS simulations

IV. CONCLUSION

A broad-band SIW antenna has been presented with good gain, the proposed antenna can be potentially used in integrated terahertz applications. The antenna results include CST and HFSS simulations, where simulations are in good agreement, and show the proposed antenna can be a good candidate for terahertz communications. In this communication, an improved antenna performance is obtained when graphene material is used for the design of SIW patch antennas.

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